

ENZYME IMMUNE ASSAY - PORTABLE MICROCOMPUTER INTERFACED SYSTEM

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Abstract

This paper describes an enzyme immune assay system interfaced with microcomputers. Developed initially for Hewlett-Packard 9825A microprocessor, the system now utilizes an Apple II Plus with two disk drives, a printer and a monitor. The system stores values read by a multi-channel spectrophotometer, keeps records and generates reports. The system was created with portability in mind and has been tested successfully in Africa. Information collected in the field is sent to a mainframe computer via modem for further statistical analysis. It functions well in the hospital, laboratory and remote field settings.

Introduction

Enzyme immune assays (EIA) are sensitive, highly accurate serologic techniques to measure circulating antigens and antibodies for a number of infectious diseases. Microadaptation of the procedure by microtiter plates permits use of a rapid multichannel reader, the Titertek MultiskanTM spectrophotometer (Flow Laboratories, Inc., McLean, Virginia). This paper reports interfacing the photometer with microcomputers in support of a seroepidemiology laboratory with unique requirements. Although usually operated in a modern research setting,

the system is highly portable and should operate in the field even independent of standard AC power supply. Furthermore, the system will read raw data from the Titertek MultiskanTM, process the data, keep records and generate the reports. The system operation is designed to accommodate those possessing only limited familiarity with computers.

Interfacing

The automated EIA system was developed using a Hewlett-Packard (HP) 9825A microprocessor/calculator with one 9885M 8-inch Flexible Drive and an HP printer. The calculator was interfaced with the Titertek MultiskanTM spectrophotometer using an HP 98133A BCD Interface. Once the above approach proved feasible, it was re-implemented on a 48K Apple II Plus computer via an RS-232-C Serial Interface, using two floppy disk drives and a Silentyper printer (Figure 1). The Apple II Plus with its much smaller and lighter printer has made the system more portable. In addition, the bigger screen and additional disk drive have enhanced data entry and data management.

Processing

The system, written in Applesoft BASIC, uses two disks, one for system software and the other for data storage. The EIA-APPLE system is menu-driven.

Figure 1. EIA-APPLE System

Figure 2. Flow of EIA-APPLE Process

The diagram in Figure 2 illustrates the process. A 96-well microtiter plate is placed in the plate carrier of the Titertek MultiskanTM which measures absorbance of visible light and prints out the absorbance values to three decimal places. The values are printed in blocks of eight wells as a cluster. The resulting output is awkward to read and interpret. However, the computer rearranges the values from the photometer into easily read 8x12 tables identical in format to the microtiter plate. The readings of each plate are stored on a disk. The corrected optical density (test well minus serum blank) for each individual sample is calculated and stored in a random access file, together with a pointer into a demographic data file.

When requested, the computer-adjusted serologic results are printed in tabular summary form including a line listing of individuals and their respective results, along with the values obtained for controls. In addition, a letter is produced to each patient giving the serologic result, its interpretation and instructions on how he/she should proceed for follow-up.

Population Profile

The demographic file is a random access file whose record number corresponds with the number used to store a corrected O.D. in a result file. Demographic data vary in contents depending on type of population and needs of the investigation.

Assay Technique and Plate Processing

Relevant antigen is diluted and adsorbed to the wells of a 96-well microtiter plate. It is then incubated overnight at 20-25°C. The antigen is removed and the plate is washed 3 times with PBS/Tween to remove any unbound antigen. Test sera are diluted and added to the wells. Specific antibody, if present will bind to the attached antigen during one-hour incubation period. Any unbound antibody is removed by washing. Enzyme conjugated species specific anti-immunoglobulin (anti-human IgG) is diluted and added to the wells. This will bind to the antigen-antibody complex already present. After a one-hour incubation period, the plate is washed to remove unbound conjugate. Enzyme substrate is added and is hydrolyzed by the bound enzyme conjugate. The reaction is stopped after a specific time and the color change is assessed spectrophotometrically. The amount and rate of the color change is proportional to the amount of specific antibody in the sera.

Current Status and Future Enhancement

The system has been successfully tested at the USUHS, as well as at a field setting in Zambia, Africa. The system has been rewritten to run in a CP/M environment, generating data bases which may be manipulated by the dBASE IITM data base manager and ABSTATTM statistical package.

Conclusion

The enzyme immune assay system when interfaced with microcomputer takes less than three minutes to process a plate and store results. It is highly cost-effective by conserving substantial amounts of technician and secretarial time. Also, the system is designed for versatility. It will function equally well in the hospital, a research laboratory, or as a portable sero-epidemiologic laboratory.

This work is partially supported by W.H.O. grant TDR810218, U.S.A.I.D. grant Sci:2H-08, and USUHS grant C08745.

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